

Effect of Type of Yeast and Yeast Concentration to The Level Ethanol in Bioethanol Production with Molasses Material

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ABSTRACT

Molasses is a byproduct of sugar manufacturing process and a sugar factory waste that can not be crystallized again with sucrose content of 48-56%. Molasses is one of the many ingredients that can be used as raw material for ethanol production. Ethanol is a volatile liquid, clear, colorless, odorless typical that can be obtained from fermentation with a substrate that contain lots of carbohydrates (sugar, starch or cellulose). The aims of this research was to investigate the effect of yeast type and yeast concentration between bread yeast and tape yeast to ethanol content obtained from the fermentation of molasses. The technique of data collected was conducted, namely fermentation which carried out during the 72 hours with bread yeast and tape yeast. It was followed by a distillation process. The result of the distillation was measured by gas chromatography hewlett paccard 5890 series II and mass spectroscopy Shimadzu QP-2010S. The data obtained were analyzed statistically by using t test and anova test with a level of 95%. The ethanol content with bread yeast and tape yeast with concentration 0,1 % (v/v); 0,2% (v/v); dan 0,5%(v/v respectively was adalah 0,40 %; 1,16 %; 2,56 % dan 0,85 %; 1,84 %; 3,66 %. Results of the test "t" showed no significant differences between bread yeast and tape yeast. In the anova test showed there are difference between the concentration of yeast 0,1%; 0,2%; and 0,5% which indicated the probability value 0,00 (<0,05).

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INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is an agrarian country that annually produces abundant natural wealth in the form of agricultural products. These agricultural products are widely used for agricultural industry activities. Every year the agricultural industry produces a large amount of waste. In the sugar or cane sugar industry, in addition to producing granulated sugar, it also produces molasses. Molasses is a type of syrup that is a by-product produced during the bleaching process of sugars that can no longer be crystallized. Molasses contains a lot of organic acids and large amounts of sugars, both sucrose and reducing sugars. The total sugar content ranges from 48 - 56% with a pH of around 5.5 - 5.6, so it is an excellent raw material for the manufacture of bioethanol. (Irvan, P. 2015: Trisakti B, 2015: Yuana, 2018)

Bioethanol is a liquid resulting from the fermentation process of sugar from carbohydrate sources (starch) using the help of microorganisms. The production of bioethanol from plants containing starch or carbohydrates is carried out through the process of converting carbohydrates into sugars (glucose) by several methods including acid hydrolysis and enzymatic. (Baharuddin, M, 2016; Banerjee, R. 2017; Ni'mah, L, 2015; Zabed, H, 2017)

In the ethanol fermentation process, the concentration of the level and type of yeast used can affect the ethanol levels produced. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research to determine the influence of yeast concentration and the type of yeast used, in this case the comparison between baker's yeast and tape yeast on ethanol levels in the production of bioethanol and for efforts to increase the economic value of molasses. (Andari, 2015; Malle, D, 2014; Ni'mah, L, 2015)

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RESEARCH METHODS

1. Equipment and Materials

The equipment used in this study includes: glass tools in general (*pyrex*) such as a set of distillations, measuring cups, glass bags, measuring flasks and erlenmeyer. Picnometers, *waterbaths*, gas stoves, thermometers, digital pH meters, vials, analytical scales, gram scales, stirring rods, watch glasses, gram and milligram weights, static-clamps, hoses and a set of Hewlett Pacard 5890 series II gas chromatography tools. The material used is class 3 molasses (*blackstrap*) obtained from the Gondang Winangun Klaten sugar factory, Central Java.

2. Work Procedure

2.1 Preparation of ethanol from molasses

33.3 mL of molasses was taken, and diluted with 100 mL of aquadest in a glass freezer (133 mL of a mixture of molasses and water). Then stirred until evenly distributed, after which the pH was measured at 4.0 – 5.0. The temperature is increased through heating until the temperature is 28-32°C above the *waterbath*. After that, it is transferred into a bottle, then mixed with yeast at a concentration of 0.1% (v/v), 0.2% (v/v) and 0.5% (v/v) in the form of a solution in aquadest of 50.0 mL, stirred until homogeneous. Tightly covered with plastic and fermented for 72 hours at room temperature. It is then distilled until ethanol is produced. (Baharuddin, M, 2016; Banerjee, R, 2015; Guerro, A, 2018; Irvan, P, 2015; Trisakti, B, 2015)

2.2 Analytical Methods

Preparation of Standard Solution 1 %

The concentrated n-butanol solution was taken with a measuring pipette of 1.24 mL to make a 10% n-butanol parent solution, then put into a 10mL measuring flask, added aquadest to the limit mark and shaken until homogeneous. A 10% n-butanol solution is taken as much as 1mL, then an aquadest is added until the mark is marked and cornered until homogeneous.

Calibration Curve Manufacturing / Standard Ethanol

Ethanol raw solution is made with a concentration of 0.5; 1; 2; 4 and 6% V/V are respectively inserted into a 10 mL measuring flask and 1 mL of 1 % n-butanol solution is added. The solution is then shaken until homogeneous.

Sample Solution Preparation

The distillate is put into a measuring flask of 10 mL until the mark is marked, then 1 mL of 1% n-butanol is added. The solution is cornered until homogeneous. The sample solution was then taken as much as 2 mL and placed in a GC sample vial to be tested for ethanol content.

Penentuan alkohol dalam sampel dengan metode GC,

The sample filtrate was maintained at 20±0.1 °C. Dissolve 2 mL of sample with 20 mL of internal standard n-butanol. Inject 0.5-1 µL of each standard ethanol solution into the GC. The same treatment was also carried out on the sample solution in n-butanol. The peak areas of the internal standard ethanol and sample were calculated. Calculation, plot the graph of the peak area of ethanol peak area of internal standard against the concentration of ethanol % V/V (after correcting for purity) (Aziz, Y.S. 2019; Coning, P.D, 2019; Dhony, 2020; Hasan, M.M, 2019; Honig, V, 2015; Muchtaridi, M.I, 2012; Paramita A, 2022; Widya, A., 2018; Yurika, 2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Measurement of ethanol content using gas chromatography

Ethanol analysis on fermented samples was carried out in 2 stages, namely, the separation stage and the quantitative level of measurement with gas chromatography to measure ethanol levels

Ethanol as a food and beverage product is produced from the fermentation process, namely from the process of carbohydrate fermentation that is enzymatically lyated. One type of enzyme converts carbohydrates into glucose then into ethanol, the other type of enzyme produces vinegar (acetic acid), with ethanol as an intermediary. Fermentation is carried out with the help of certain yeast species such as *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*. This yeast metabolizes sugar (glucose) in the absence of oxygen to produce ethanol and CO₂. (Aziz, Y.S. 2019; Coning, P.D, 2019; Dhony, 2020; Hasan, M.M, 2019; Honig, V, 2015; Muchtaridi, M.I, 2012; Paramita A, 2022; Widya, A., 2018; Yurika, 2022)

Determination of ethanol levels using the GC method can be done because ethanol is a volatile compound. The process is carried out by means of an ethanol solution being injected using a micro syringe into the GC separator column. At the injection site, the ethanol solution immediately evaporates and enters the column along with the inert carrier gas. In the GC column, the separation of gas components occurs according to the boiling point and polarity of each compound. The gas components that have been separated then exit the column and enter the detector, then the detected signal is recorded on the recorder or integrator. The ethanol content can be determined by calculating the peak area of the ethanol chromatogram recorded on the recorder. (Aziz, Y.S. 2019; Coning, P.D, 2019; Dhony, 2020; Hasan, M.M, 2019; Honig, V, 2015; Malle, D. 2014; Mc.Nair, H.M, 2011; Muchtaridi, M.I, 2012; Paramita A, 2022; Widya, A., 2018; Yurika, 2022)

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Tabel 1. Results of ethanol content measurement by Gas Chromatography (GC)

Replication	Baker's yeast			Tapai Yeast		
	Baker's yeast concentration			Concentration of tape yeast		
	0,1 %	0,2 %	0,5 %	0,1 %	0,2 %	0.5 %
1	0,44 %	1,14 %	2,49 %	0,91 %	1,96 %	3,11 %
2	0,38 %	1,17 %	2,54 %	0,81 %	1,83%	3,26 %
3	0,37 %	1,16 %	2,66 %	0,82 %	2,02 %	4,60 %
4	0,40 %	1,15 %	2,53 %	0,83 %	1,55 %	3,55 %
5	0,41 %	1,17 %	2,58 %	0,87 %	1,85%	3,78 %
X	0,40 %	1,16 %	2,56 %	0,85 %	1,84 %	3,66 %

2. Ethanol content measurement by gas chromatography (GC) Hewlett Paccard 5890 series II

Figure 1. Graph of ethanol levels of baker's yeast and tape's yeast

The ethanol levels of baker's yeast and tape's yeast with concentrations of 0.1%; 0.2%; and 0.5% respectively were 0.40%; 1.16%; 2.56% and 0.85%; 1.84%; 3.66%. A higher number of initial cells will accelerate the adaptation phase. The amount of concentration of 0.5 % is higher when compared to the concentration of 0.1 % and 0.2 %. This larger amount of yeast makes the ability of yeast to produce enzymes and break down sucrose into glucose even greater so that the number of enzymes produced is also more. With more glucose formed, the ethanol levels produced are greater. So that in the fermentation time of 72 hours, the yeast concentration of 0.5% has the highest ethanol content when compared to the concentration of 0.1% and 0.2%.. (Dirayati, A.G, 2020)(Yuana, S.E.N, 2018)(Zabed, H.S, 2017)

In addition, yeast has different microbial content. The main microbe in baker's yeast is *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.. Yeast for tapai is a mixed population of genera where there are species of the genus *Aspergillus*, genus *Saccharomyces*, genus *Candida*, genus *Hansenula*. The genus lives together synergistically. *Aspergillus* can simplify amylum, while *Saccharomyces*, *Candida* and *Hansenula* can decompose sugars into ethanol. Due to the synergistic work of microbial cultures contained in tape yeast, the number of enzymes produced to convert glucose increases when compared to baker's yeast, causing the ethanol levels produced to be different when compared to baker's yeast. (Hasanah, H, 2012; Muchtaridi, M.I, 2012, Mohammed, A.D.H, 2018; Trisakti, 2015; Zabed, H, 2017)

Polysaccharides will be broken down into simpler carbohydrates. The well-known process of glycolysis or breakdown of glucose is the Embden-Meyerhoff Parnas (EMP) pathway. This glucose breakdown pathway consists of several stages and in principle this process is the breakdown of glucose into pyruvic acid. This path will be continued at a later stage if the expected result is ethanol. The reaction of converting pyruvic acid to ethanol starts from the conversion of pyruvic acid to acetaldehyde through the process of decarboxylase. The decarboxylase process is the loss of one carboxyl group into acetaldehyde and then reduced to alcohol.(Baharuddin,M. 2016;Dirayati,A.G, 2017)

The chromatogram results based on ethanol measurements with gas chromatography can be seen in figure 2 (baker's yeast) and figure 3 (tape yeast).

Figure 2. Chromatogram of gas chromatography measurements (Bread Yeast)

Figure 3. Chromatogram of gas chromatography measurement (Yeast Tape)

The results of the gas chromatography measurements above show the *peak* and area counts of the ethanol and propanol samples. The peak is the result of a qualitative analysis of gas chromatography, this analysis provides an overview of what compounds are detected by gas chromatography. Meanwhile, area *counts* are a quantitative analysis indicated by measuring ethanol levels.

The retention time of the measurement results indicates the polarity of a compound. The polarity properties of ethanol and propanol are different, ethanol is more polar while propanol is non-polar. Propanol is an internal standard solution, that is, a standard solution added to an ethanol sample. Its function is to control injection errors in measurements by gas chromatography. The stationary phase used in measurements with non-polar gas chromatography is found in the column of the gas chromatography tool, the detector used is the FID (*Flame Ionization Detector*) type. The more polar the compound enters the column, the faster the compound will flow into the detector because the compound will not be retained in the column for long, this is based on the working system of a gas chromatography device that undergoes a reverse phase. So the first peak shows ethanol compounds while the second peak shows propanol compounds.

3. Determination of the molecular structure of organic compounds and the molecular weight of compounds.

The mass spectrum of baker's yeast ethanol is presented in figure 4 and for the mass spectrum of tapai yeast ethanol is presented in figure 5 and the mass spectrum of ethanol compounds is presented in figure 6.

Figure 4. Mass spectrum of baker's yeast fermentation compounds

Figure 5. Mass spectrum of compounds from fermentation of tapai yeast

Figure 6. Mass spectrum of ethanol compounds

Above is a picture of three spectrums, the spectrum of compounds resulting from the fermentation of baker's yeast, tape yeast, and the spectrum of ethanol compounds. The spectrum of fermented compounds shows the same fragmentation results as the spectrum of ethanol compounds. The spectrum of compounds from the fermentation of baker's yeast and tape yeast above shows that the compounds are ethanol. The spectrum of fermentation results of tape yeast appeared at a retention time of 2.161 minutes and baker's yeast appeared at a retention time of 2.162 minutes. Ethanol compounds bombarded with high-energy electrons result in the release of one electron of the ethanol compound, by releasing one radical hydrogen atom resulting in fragments with m/z 45. Another fragment formed with a value of m/z 31 obtained from ethanol releases methyl radical compounds. Another fragmentation with a value of m/z 29, ethanol compounds release hydroxyl radicals. The ethanol fragmentation pattern is presented in figure 7.

Figure 7. Ethanol fragmentation patterns

CONCLUSION

1. The type of yeast has no effect on ethanol levels
2. Yeast concentration affects ethanol levels from molasses fermentation
3. Molasses can be fermented into ethanol by baker's yeast and tape yeast. Ethanol content in baker's yeast concentration 0.1 %; 0,2 %; and 0.5% respectively is 0.40%; 1,16 %; and 2.56 percent. The ethanol content in fermented yeast concentration is 0.1 %; 0,2 %; and 0.5% respectively is 0.85%; 1,84 %; and 3.66 percent.

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